

Breaking Gender Barriers in Computer Science: Exploring the Impact of Digital Fabrication Workshops in Smart Environments

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Abstract. Gender barriers in Computer Science (CS) are undeniable. The lack of girls and (young) women participating in CS is unacceptable in several ways. Reasons to explain this gap are given in the literature: First, CS has a reputation as a heavily technology-focused subject with no particular social or practical application references. But in particular, also computer scientists are highly stereotyped and these clichés often are at odds with girls' and young women's self-concepts. These causes yield targets for interventions through extracurricular activities that are presented in this paper.

In total, 90 digital fabrication workshops were evaluated through pre-post-questionnaires to develop a richer understanding of the effect of digital fabrication workshops in smart environments designed to reduce biases and attract girls and young women aged 9 to 18 to CS. In particular, the change of the participants' image of CS in general, their self-efficacy in dealing with technology, the perceived social relevance of CS, and the perceived relevance of CS for later professional life were investigated. Our results indicate that digital fabrication workshops can indeed contribute both to a richer understanding of what CS is and to a small increase in technic related self-efficacy. The findings also provide a basis for deriving implications for the realization of Informatics or CS as a subject matter in primary and secondary education.

Keywords: Computer Science Education · Participation · Gender · Digital Fabrication · Smart Environments

1 Introduction

Computer Science Education (CSE) in schools is handled as diverse as possible in Germany: it ranges from compulsory subject to elective subject to no subject. Initiatives like the Informatics for All Coalition claim for informatics as a foundational discipline in schools across Europe⁴ and also various German committees

⁴ <https://www.informaticsforall.org/>, retrieved June 6th, 2023

are eager to promote CS as a compulsory subject throughout the country⁵. A very strong argument why CS should be a compulsory subject in schools is to empower everyone to actively participate in today's digitalized world [10, 17]. Moreover, it has been stated that this point is crucial for female participation which addresses a very important aspect in today's society [5].

Today's western world is widely driven by technology in almost every area of life: traffic, policies, journalism, culture, and also personal life that includes well-being, security or organizing. Hence, it is important to give women and girls a voice in technology development. Past product developments have shown that if women are not involved in designing them, products risk to fail at addressing women's needs. This can be annoying, derogatory, or even dangerous for women and diverse other people [18, 26]. It is when a homogeneous group of people is delegated to design for the future that diverse needs risk being ignored.

Accordingly, a compulsory subject could be an important step to more female participation in CS. Nevertheless, it can be taught in diverse ways. Our ideas of modern CSE include digital fabrication activities as they offer the possibility to 'do' CS while relating to the discipline and its applications in a hands-on activity. In our project, we focused on digital fabrication activities for girls to find out what aspects might contribute to more female participation in CS.

In this paper we present reasons for the lack of female participation in CS and how digital fabrication might address them. We then describe workshop activities that were designed, conducted and evaluated with respect to attract girls to CS. Results regarding the image of CS, girl's self-efficacy, and the perceived relevance of CS are presented and discussed. We conclude with arguments for digital fabrication as part of compulsory CSE at schools.

2 Background

In Europe we face the problem that only about 20% of all undergraduate CS students are female [27]. These numbers vary depending on the level of education (bachelor or master) and also on the European country. In German senior classes in CS only 16% of school students are female [11]. Regarding the question of why there are so few women in CS there are many different explanations that cannot be regarded separately but as a combination of many aspects. Vainionpää et al. present aspects that affect girls' career choices regarding IT that include influences by people in the girls' environment as well as historical issues such as stereotypes and images of the field [28]. Further studies confirmed that it is partly the girls' personal environment that prevents girls from choosing a career in IT or that it is more the image of people than doing CS that hampers more diversity in the field [12, 29]. Another important aspect when it comes to girls and their perception of CS is self-efficacy [2, 8]. While boys tend to overestimate themselves, girls undervalue their abilities which results in girls being less confident in their skills and enjoying CS activities less than boys [24].

⁵ <https://www.shetransformsit.org/>, retrieved June 6th, 2023

However, studies reveal that girls perform better in computer and information literacy tasks and also that they show higher CS abstraction abilities after a CS introductory course than boys [9, 23]. Nevertheless, another study shows that there is a significant difference in abilities between boys and girls when there is no compulsory CSE in schools [25].

Hence, the question arises how to create a CS environment that is more appealing to girls than it has been so far. Therefore, in diverse projects digital fabrication activities have been used to raise more interest in STEM, especially technology, in a creative and informal way. Here, we refer to digital fabrication as creative interdisciplinary construction activity with physical computing kits that comprise the design, building (constructing) and programming of smart objects using hardware (controllers, sensors, actuators), desktop programming environments and crafting materials including 3D-printers and laser-cutters and that allow for creativity and personally meaningful projects.

Digital fabrication activities, such as creating personally meaningful smart textile artifacts show potentials to raise girls' self-efficacy in dealing with technology [16]. Further, learning activities with e-textiles combine traditional crafting practices with CS and show potential to broaden participation in IT [13, 4]. Generally, physical computing toolkits have been utilized to introduce CS concepts in a meaningful, hands-on way for a long time [3]. Relating computing activities to participants' everyday life is another crucial point that can be implemented in digital fabrication activities [17]. Furthermore, physical computing adds state-of-the-art topics to the CS curriculum, such as sensing and control or ubiquitous and embedded systems [20].

3 Breaking gender barriers in CS: The SMILE project

The SMILE project aimed at enhancing female participation in CS by cultivating a positive image of CS through digital fabrication workshops. By means of the innovative topic of smart environments and a coordinated didactic concept, in digital fabrication workshops girls and young women from the age of nine to 18 were encouraged to create their own intelligent environmental artifacts, such as smart pillows, lights, closets, plants, or magical rooms and houses. The project was conducted over three years in three cities in Germany, namely Hamburg, Bremen, and Oldenburg. Construction of artifacts included programming microcontrollers, i.e. Arduino (Lily Pad), Calliope mini, ESP8266, connection of sensors and actuators if necessary, and integration into objects such as pillows or plants. In most of the workshops, additional digital fabrication tools were used, e.g. to 3D-print artificial flowers [19] or to create personally designed smart pillows using vinyl-cutters [6].

Topics that are appealing to girls within the scope of smart environments were worked out in pre-workshops [14] and chosen according to age, previous knowledge, and lab facilities. Each workshop involved 12-15 girls or young women, comprised up to 20 hours, and was accompanied by two to three facilitators. Workshops took place in university settings in living labs, university FabLabs,

or alike and were conducted by seven different partners. Drawing from previous studies and research, the overall workshop concept incorporated the highlighting of specific aspects of CS during the interventions, including an introduction to the fundamentals of CS as well as the practical relevance of CS in our everyday lives. If possible and suitable, research labs (mostly ambient assisted living labs or living places) were visited to better illustrate what CS research is about and how it relates to real life.

Preliminary findings indicated a positive impact of digital fabrication workshops on girls' attitudes of CS in terms of stereotypes, scope, and its presence. In particular, participating in a digital fabrication workshop made the field appear more female and more ubiquitous than before [15] and resulted in higher confidence regarding programming skills [22]. In the present study, data from all 90 workshops carried out over the project period of three years is analyzed, providing a comprehensive overview compared to previous partial studies.

For the evaluation of the project, participants completed computer-based questionnaires at the beginning and the end of each workshop. Since answering questions was optional, the number of included participants in the pre-/post-comparison differs between these items. Additionally, the data evaluated fulfilled the following two conditions: the participants were taking part in the workshop for the first time and the specific questions were answered at both measuring points.

To test for pre-/post-changes in the items image of CS in general, self-efficacy in dealing with technology, social relevance of CS and relevance of CS for later professional life, paired sample t-tests were conducted. Effect sizes were calculated according to Cohen's d as implemented in the R-package "effsize". To test whether changes between pre- and post-measurement points were related to the participants age, attendance of CS classes in school or parental background, Spearman correlations were conducted between those ratings and pre-/post-changes in the respective variables of interest. Sample sizes differ from 262 to 500 between the tests, because only complete cases were included into the analyses.

4 Results

Within the scope of this paper, we focus on the following concepts and questions, which were surveyed in the pre- and post-questionnaire: image of CS in general, self efficacy in dealing with technology, social relevance of CS, and relevance of CS for later professional life.

4.1 Image of CS in general

The following visual analog scale⁶ statements have been combined to assess the image of CS in general:

⁶ As with the following items (cf. Sec. 4.3 and 4.4), the values of the sliders were mapped to a scale of 1-100 to ensure comparability.

Computer Science is ...
 ... *difficult/easy*
 ... *narrowly focused/just about anywhere*
 ... *boring/exciting*
 ... *uninteresting/interesting*
 ... *illogical/logical*
 ... *monotonous/diversified*

Higher values indicate a more positive image of CS.

To test whether the rating of the image of CS in general was higher in the post- compared to the pre-testing we performed a paired t-test. We found a significant effect (CS-image-pre: $M = 68.67$, $SD = 13.71$, CS-image-post: $M = 73.48$, $SD = 13.62$; $t_{1,261} = 7.15$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.4$). This indicates that the participant's image of CS in general was more positive in the post- compared to the pre-testing. Participant's views changed most on the statement that CS is just about anywhere (from 55.5/100 to 65.5/100). Moderate changes occurred on the questions on CS being exciting, interesting, and diversified, whereas the initial values were rather high (70/100 to 82/100) and increased by 3.8 to 5.9 points. Almost no change was registered on the question of CS being difficult or easy, whereas values pointed slightly more towards difficult (45.8/100 to 46.5/100).

A Spearman correlation did not reveal any significant association between pre-post changes of the image of CS in general and age ($\rho_{364} = 0.05$, $p = .78$).

To test whether participants' change of the image of CS in general from pre- to post-measurements was related to whether the girls attend CS classes at school, we performed a Spearman correlation, no significant association was obtained ($\rho_{365} = 0.02$, $p = .78$).

4.2 Self-efficacy in dealing with technology

To determine the girls' self-efficacy in dealing with technology, we used the questionnaire "Control beliefs in dealing with technology" (KUT) [1], which was adapted to the age of the girls and newer technologies (e.g. tablet instead of video recorder in the description; modified KUT). The following questions were queried to rate on a 5-point Likert scale and polarity reversed if necessary:

1. *I can solve quite a few of the technical problems I face on my own.*
2. *Technical devices are often complicated to operate and understand.*
3. *I really enjoy facing technical challenges.*
4. *Because I have never had problems with technology, this will also be the case in the future.*
5. *I feel so helpless in dealing with technical equipment that I don't even try it alone.*
6. *Even if I do not manage to operate a technical device immediately, I do not give up.*
7. *When I solve a technical task on my own, it is usually by chance.*
8. *Most technical tasks are so complicated that it makes no sense for me to deal with them on my own.*

Higher values indicate higher self-efficacy while 8 represents the lowest and 40 the highest possible scoring.

To test whether the self-efficacy in dealing with technology (modified KUT) scoring was higher in the post- compared to the pre-testing, we performed a paired t-test. We found a significant effect (KUT-pre: $M = 28.02$, $SD = 4.8$, KUT-post: $M = 28.42$, $SD = 5.03$; $t_{1,499} = 2.22$, $p = .03$, $d = 0.1$). In other words, our data provide evidence that the participant's self-efficacy in dealing with technology were slightly higher in the post- compared to the pre-testing.

A Spearman correlation revealed a significant positive association between pre-post changes of self-efficacy in dealing with technology and age ($\rho_{498} = 0.12$, $p = .009$). That is, our data indicate that a stronger positive gain in self-efficacy from pre- to post-measurement can be found in older participants compared to the younger ones.

A Spearman correlation showed a significant positive association between pre-post changes of self-efficacy in dealing with technology and whether the girls attend CS classes at school ($\rho_{498} = 0.13$, $p = .009$). That is, our data indicate that participants who state to attend CS classes in school have a stronger positive gain in self-efficacy from pre- to post-measurement.

A significant negative association between pre-post changes of self-efficacy in dealing with technology and pre-scores regarding parental technology communication and encouragement ($\rho_{495} = -0.10$, $p = .009$) was indicated by a Spearman correlation. That is, our data indicate that participants who hardly communicate about technical related topics with their parents and experience little encouragement to occupy oneself with technology have a stronger positive gain in self-efficacy from pre- to post-measurement.

4.3 Perceived social relevance of CS

To investigate how relevant girls consider CS for society, we asked them to rate the following statement on a visual analog scale with higher values indicating higher relevance:

*Computer Science is ...
... unimportant for society/important for society*

To test whether participants rated CS as more socially relevant in the post-compared to the pre-testing, we performed a paired t-test. No significant effect was obtained (soci-relevance-pre: $M = 76.67$, $SD = 22.10$, soci-relevance-post: $M = 75.74$, $SD = 26.50$; $t_{1,432} = 0.71$, $p = .50$, $d = 0.03$).

To test whether participants' change of the social relevance of CS from pre- to post-measurements was related to the girls' age, we performed a Spearman correlation, no significant association was obtained ($\rho_{431} = 0.02$, $p = .72$).

A Spearman correlation did not reveal any significant association between pre-post changes of the social relevance of CS and whether the girls attend CS classes at school ($\rho_{431} = 0.02$, $p = .67$).

4.4 Perceived relevance of CS for later professional life

To assess how relevant girls consider CS for their later professional life, we asked them to rate the following statement on a visual analog scale:

Computer Science is ...

... important for my future professional life/unimportant for my future professional life

Higher values indicate higher relevance.

To test whether participants rated CS as more relevant for their later professional life in the post- compared to the pre-testing, we performed a paired t-test. No significant effect was obtained (prof-relevance-pre: $M = 62.01$, $SD = 26.89$, prof-relevance-post: $M = 62.01$, $SD = 29.13$; $t_{1,405} = 0.02$, $p = .85$, $d < 0.001$).

A Spearman correlation was conducted between pre-post changes in ratings of relevance of CS for later professional life and the participant's age. We did not find a significant association ($\rho_{404} = 0.05$, $p = 0.29$).

To test whether participants' pre-post changes in ratings of relevance of CS for later professional life was related to whether the girls attend CS classes at school, we performed a Spearman correlation, no significant association was obtained ($\rho_{403} = 0.08$, $p = .11$).

A significant negative association between pre-post changes of rating relevance of CS for their later professional life and pre-scores regarding parental technology communication and encouragement ($\rho_{380} = -0.15$, $p = .003$) was indicated by a Spearman correlation. That is, our data indicate that participants who hardly communicate about technical related topics with their parents and experience little encouragement to occupy oneself with technology have a stronger positive gain regarding rating relevance of CS for their later professional life from pre- to post-measurement compared to the ones who communicate more with their parents at home.

5 Discussion

In the present study, we aimed to develop a richer understanding of the effect of digital fabrication workshops in smart environments designed to attract girls and young women aged 9 to 18 to CS. Specifically, we expected a change from pre- to post-measurement towards a more positive image of CS in general, higher self-efficacy scorings, and a higher assessment of the social relevance of CS as well as the relevance for their own later professional life. Results show a significant positive change for the image of CS in general and technology related self-efficacy but neither for the social relevance of CS nor for the relevance of CS for later professional life in general. Nevertheless, we argue for digital fabrication workshops as part of regular CS education as ways of engaging more girls into CS because of these findings which we will discuss here.

5.1 Discussion of Results

The positive change regarding the image of CS among the participating girls is in line with our previous research in this field and in this project [7, 15]. At this point, we can infer that the topic of smart environments is as convenient to get an insight into CS as topics from former studies that use other scenarios. We should keep in mind though that during the workshops it was further discussed what CS is and who is working in this field. Hence, we cannot say that it is merely creating smart environment objects that leads to a more positive image of CS. We argue that the whole workshop process needs to be related to CS processes, such as designing a new IT product as a solution for a specific kind of problem. Further, diverse people in the field should be mentioned including women, people of color, etc.

A closer look on the separate questions regarding the image of the field supports the general idea that digital fabrication workshops are a way to show the prevalence of CS in today's (western) world and its diversity. Further, it seems to be a way to highlight appealing aspects of CS. Anyhow, it also indicates that CS does (almost) not appear easier than before, which might be a realistic estimation of CS contents.

Self-efficacy among girls also raised after they participated in a digital fabrication workshop. This effect has been shown in previous research before (e.g. [7, 16, 21]) and has been proved here to be valid for smart environment settings as well. Self-efficacy is an important issue when it comes to girls and CS because research has also revealed that girls and women tend to underestimate themselves which is regarded as one of the reasons why they do not aim for a career in STEM related fields [28, 2]. Hence, we argue for CS activities that raise girls' self-efficacy in dealing with technology as much as possible and see clear benefits in digital fabrication workshops where girls are empowered to create their own smart object.

Most interestingly, in this study, we found correlations between self-efficacy and girls' family surroundings and whether they attend CS classes at school or not. First, our results indicate that self-efficacy raises more among girls from families that do not communicate about technology at home than their peers who do. One reason might be that the ones with parents who communicate about technology already have a better understanding about technology and their own relation to it than the ones who do not have the opportunity to talk about technology at home. Therefore, we argue that it would be advisable to run digital fabrication workshops (extensively) in schools so that every girl has the possibility to relate herself to technology and to raise her self-efficacy in dealing with technology. This could be a step towards more equal opportunities. Further, the ones who attend CS classes at school benefited more regarding their increase of self-efficacy than the ones without CS classes at schools. This effect might be rooted in the current style of CS classes which some of the girls reported as less interesting or only learning how to use IT instead of solving problems or creating new artifacts. Hence, we would suggest integrating digital fabrication into CS classes at school where possible.

Against our expectations, we did not find significant improvements regarding the social relevance of CS. We ascribe this to the rather high initial values (77/100) and that the participants were mostly aware of the relevance of CS in people’s everyday life before participating in one of our digital fabrication workshops.

Finally, there were no general improvements regarding the relevance of CS for their own later professional life, but a small negative correlation to parents’ communication and encouragement. Again, as a step towards more equal opportunities in terms of creating communication opportunities for girls who do not talk to their parents about technology, we argue for digital fabrication workshops in schools.

One reason for not finding general improvements regarding the relevance of CS for participant’s own later professional life might be that the professional career of our participants is still rather far away (age M: 12.7, SD: 1.9). Another explanation might be that many of the objects that were built during the workshops did not have the character of a real-life technology or a serious functionality like the talking plants or the smart pillows. Although some of the objects targeted a real-life purpose such as smart bookshelves or book recommendation systems, the workshops might have been regarded more as “play” than as serious work. At this point, more research is needed on how to make use of digital fabrication workshops for opening up minds for possible career paths, especially for girls.

5.2 Limitations

Our study is limited in several aspects. First of all, we cannot clearly say that all our findings are only related to the workshops. Other impacts might have come from their surroundings during the runtime of the workshop as well, such as influences by their peers, parents or others, or even by extremely hot weather, which might have led to a loss or gain of motivation, etc. Further, the workshops were all short-term interventions and changes were measured between the beginning and the end of the workshop. We cannot say anything about long term effects of workshops on girls’ mindsets and future behaviors. More research is needed here.

The survey was implemented as a pre-post-online-test, whereas girls started their workshop experience by filling out the first questionnaire. Tutors were aside for helping with rather technical questions, but they were instructed not to talk about contents in order to avoid influencing the participants. This way, some questions were skipped and we cannot assure that the girls understood all details of questions appropriately.

Further, all of the workshops that were conducted differ in their details. Generally, they all follow the same concept, but tutors, locations, technology, lab visits and topics differed within the workshops. Also, acquisition of the participating girls differed which leads to diverse motivational aspects. That is, we cannot say which detail exactly led to a specific change and which did not. Our

results rely on the wholistic concept of engaging girls in creating smart environment objects including relating it to CS. Impacts of specific details remain unknown.

6 Conclusion

Summing up, these mostly extracurricular digital fabrication activities have shown different positive effects for girls, that are interesting for CSE in general. First, it was shown that the activities led to a more positive attitude regarding the image of CS, which is very important when it comes to participation and learning. Therefore, we see potential of digital fabrication activities as part of CSE in schools, especially when the subject is perceived as abstract and boring by school students.

Second, it was confirmed that attending a digital fabrication workshop can lead to a higher self-efficacy. As self-efficacy increases even more with a higher age of the participants and in some states of Germany CS lessons start at an older age, again it might be beneficial to implement such activities at school, because even at an older age, self-efficacy can be addressed appropriately. Further, a higher increase was measured when participants attended CS lessons in schools. Hence, we argue for digital fabrication activities as part of CSE because it seems to be a reasonable methodological supplement to what has been part of participants' school lessons before.

Finally, from our results we infer that digital fabrication activities in a compulsory school subject contribute to more equal opportunities for girls and all school students. The ones who do not speak with their parents about technology show a higher increase of self-efficacy regarding technology and also the perceived relevance of computer skills for later professional life increase only in this case. That is, the activities offer valuable opportunities for later life, which would be less available for students whose parents do not speak about technology with them.

Overall, we argue that the compulsory school subject CS should contain digital fabrication activities in means of contemporary CSE. This 'doing' CS conveys an appropriate image of what CS is and allows for equal opportunities for all when it comes to participating in a digitally networked world.

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